

On page 8, the author would like to amend the following.

*If the extreme definition of “unnecessary home charges” as used by T. Mukherjee is used to define “drain”; the amounts involved were 0.04% to 0.07% of the national income over the whole period 1870-1900.*

Should read:

*If the extreme definition of “unnecessary home charges” as used by T. Mukherjee is used to define “drain”; the amounts involved were 0.4% of the GNP [in an era when national income per capita made substantial gains], over the whole period 1870-1900.*